

A preliminary study on the ethno-botany in Deuli Forest Range, Baripada Forest Division, Baripada, Odisha

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Date of receipt: 27.08.2021

Date of acceptance: 27.10.2021

ABSTRACT

The present study reveals the traditional knowledge of people in utilizing plants for their ethno-botanical potential. Hakims, Vaidyas, and locally available unrecorded information from tribal peoples of three panchayats under Baripada forest division, Mayurbhanj district of Odisha., were recorded. An extensive field survey of the entire area of Saragchhida, Chandua, and Nandana was made and information from tribal peoples and Vaidyas were collected. The ethno-botanical study was carried out during February - March 2021 to document the medicinal utility of plants by the practitioner. A list of 69 species of medicinal plants belonging to 66 genera and 41 families was made. A total of 58 species of dicotyledons and 11 species of monocotyledons were recorded from the whole study. The study explained the administration and indication with respect to different diseases, and injuries along with their vernacular names, botanical names, and plant parts used. The documented medicinal plants and the knowledge they acquired to cure the diseases like information on diarrhoea, jaundice, and headache, night fever, piles, etc. were provided.

Key words: Ethno-botanical study, medicinal plants, traditional knowledge

INTRODUCTION

‘Ethno-botany’ is a multifaceted knowledge that deals with the study of interactions between indigenous peoples and plants (Panigrahy and Behera, 2016). Ethno botanical studies are totally based on practices, observations and experiences and are transferred from generation to generation (Manjunath, 1990). The study shows how people of a particular culture and region make use of indigenous plants for various purposes. Plants having medicinal value are traditional, affordable, and accessible. The term ‘Ethno botany’ is extensively related to indigenous flora which is responsible for not only medicines but also for many aspects of life such as foods, clothing, intoxicants, etc. The present study reveals the ethno botanical importance of three villages of Baripada Forest Division. The study focuses on the medicinal value of the local flora found in the entire study area.

India is one of the seventy mega-diversity countries in the world with about 50000 angiospermic species (Sahu and Pattanaik, 2011), on an average 70% of India’s population is dependent on traditional medicine (Sahu and Pattanaik, 2011).

The inhabitants mainly depend on the forest as well as their gardens to fulfil the above needs. Simlipal is known as the treasure house to various valuable medicated flora (herbs, shrubs, trees, climbers) in a broad sense are responsible for the existence of the word ‘Ayurveda’ in Odisha since time immemorial. As nearer to the Biosphere Reserve, the locals have rich knowledge on the curative and preventive properties of plants that are used as medicines for them and their pets. But the preservation and documentation of this knowledge about the medicinal uses are on the borderline. The tribal people are not willing to share this type of knowledge with a stranger with a belief that the medicine will lose its healing property if too

many heads know about the use. Therefore, here is an attempt to document the knowledge of the aboriginals concerning the indigenous plants.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Fig. 1. Study area map

Baripada is a town situated in the Mayurbhanj district of Odisha. It is characterized by an equitable temperature throughout the year. We have selected places like Chandua, Saragchhida, and Nadana for our study. The detailed methodology was implemented for the fieldwork, data collection, and analysis of the information gathered as per the requirement of the study, various interview-based surveys were implemented with the local inhabitants of study area to know the administration and precaution of doses of medicinal plants.

The study was conducted during February – March 2021. The field surveys of Saragchhida, Chandua, and Nandana panchayat were done by the door-to-door investigation of various tribal peoples living in the village to know how they are utilizing the medicinal plants to get cured from any type of diseases and injuries. Plant specimens were collected and labelled with their local name, parts used, and ethno medicinal uses. In consideration of the medicinal utility of plants, the samples were collected and identified with the help of regional floras and previous literature. The plant parts used to treat different diseases and the whole information of utilization was united by the method of ethno botanical investigation. Pictorial data of each specimen were collected by using Nikon D3300 with a kit lens. During the study,

weekly observations were carried out to identify the plant species. The authenticity of the ethno botanical importance of species was examined in detail by the standard pieces of literature (Gamble and Fischer, 1915-36; Haines, 1921-25; Saxena and Dutta, 1975; Chopra et al., 1956; Chopra and Chopra, 1982; Sahoo, 1986; Saxena and Brahmam, 1994-96; Warriar et al., 1994-96; Girach et al., 1996; Pattanaik et al., 2008; Mohapatra, 2019).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

After calibrating the identity, the medicinal plant species were referred to their associated families and arranged alphabetically. The arrangement of data is presented in the form of families followed by botanical name, common name habit of the plant species, medicinal uses, and the administration for the diseases. A total of 69 species belonging to 41 families were recorded from the whole survey. Out of this 35-tree species followed by 15 species of shrubs, 12 species of Herbs, 4 species of climbers, 2 species of grasses, and 1 species of aquatic plant were recorded (Fig. 6). 85 % species of dicotyledons and 15% monocotyledons plants species were recorded.

The present study revealed that the tribal people are greatly depending on forest and forest resources (mainly flora and floral parts) for their medicines. They prefer homemade Ayurvedic medicines by the local Vaidyas (Table 1) as they have a great belief in Ayurveda. They use plant parts like stem, roots, fruits, flowers, bulbs, seeds, bark, rhizomes, etc. in different forms like powder, pulp, juice, paste, oil, decoction, exudates from plant parts. Some of the information about the uses provided in this study is new, as they have not been reported earlier.

The current study showed that the Poaceae family being dominated in this area in the case of medicinal plants followed by Euphorbiaceae, Rutaceae, Fabaceae, etc. The Poaceae family bears the responsibility of curing diseases like gastric problems, blood purification, skin diseases, blood pressure, dysentery, nasal problems, scorpion bites, etc., that of Euphorbiaceae used in case of diarrhoea, skin infection, vision improvement, to

check rheumatism, etc. All the plant families with their respective curative properties are listed in (Table 2).

The plants found in the study area are used mostly for leaves (Fig. 4) in case of their medicinal properties followed by fruits, roots, and seeds, etc. The locals use different forms of plant parts to cure from different diseases e.g., in juice form (33 plants), in paste form (19 plants), as oil (2 plants), as ashes (1 plant), as a decoction (3 plants), as powdery form (5 plants), as plant extracts (5 plants), gum (1 plant) and as an infusion (1 plant) (Fig. 5), etc. All the plant parts were used orally (62 plants), Ext. (26 plants), or by inhalation (4 plants). From the study area of 8 plant species were recorded having curative properties to dysentery followed by 7 plant species were responsible to cure skin infection, 6 plant species were responsible to cure diarrhea, 3 plant species used to cure blood pressure, 2 plant species for heart disease, cancer, and night- blindness, 1 plant species each for malaria, snake- bite and scorpion bite, etc.

CONCLUSION

The entire study area is a grand repository of indigenous as well as exotic medicinal plant varieties and the main cause of the diminution of highly potential medicinal plants are human encroachments such as unplanned developmental works, habitat loss, overexploitation, etc. Hence, appropriate conservation and protection are needed. For this vital work to be done, we should have to know the status and aspects of medicinal plants. For the conservation of these charismatic and aromatic plants, medicinal gardens should be developed in educational and research institutions. The conservation can be performed both by *ex-situ* and *in-situ* preservation practices. The indigenous, as well as the exotic plant species, need to be conserved at National and International levels by Government sponsorships. In order to propagate the cultivation and preservation of medicinal plants, the locals need to be educated and trained with various modern techniques. This vital knowledge on plants should be kept safe in their tradition as this knowledge comes from generation to generation by practices, and we cannot afford the loss of this type of knowledge in near future.

Table 1. List of *Vaidyas*, and traditional health care (human and livestock) practitioners residing within the study area

Name	Age	Sex	Tribe	Panchayat	Area of specialization
Udaya Hembrum	60	Male	Santhal	Kathagandia	Diabetes, Night-fever and Gastric
Biren Hembrum	45	Male	Santhal	Kathagandia	Jaundice
Purna Hembrum	36	Male	Santhal	Chandua	Jaundice, Fever, Diabetes
Ramananda Mahanta	90	Male	Kudmi	Nodana	Diabetes, Night-fever and Gastric.

Table 2. List of medicinal plants with administration and parts used

Family	Scientific name	Local name	Habit	Medicinal use	Part used	Methods of use
Acanthaceae	<i>Justicia adhatoda</i>	Basanga	Shrub	Cholera, piles	Leaf, Stem	Paste (Ext., Ora.)
Anacardiaceae	<i>Buchanania lanzan</i>	Chara	Tree	Diarrhoea	Bark, seed	Seed oil and bark extract (Ora.)
	<i>Mangifera indica</i>	Amba	Tree	Dysentery	Stem Bark	Fruit and leaf (Ora., Ext.)

Family	Scientific name	Local name	Habit	Medicinal use	Part used	Methods of use
Anacardiaceae	<i>Anacardium occidentale</i>	Kaju	Tree	Stomach, intestinal uses	Leaf, bark, Seed	Juice (Ora.)
Amaryllidaceae	<i>Allium sativum</i>	Rasuna	Herb	High blood pressure, common cold, heart disease, ear problem	Clove	Juice, Clove (Ora.)
Apiaceae	<i>Centella asiatica</i>	Thalkudi	Herb	Gastrointestinal	Leaf	Leaf juice (Ora.)
Apocynaceae	<i>Catharanthus roseus</i>	Sadabihari	Shrub	Dysentery	Leaf, root	Leaf Juice (Ora.)
	<i>Holarrhena pubescens</i>	Korei	Shrub	Malaria	Bark	Decoction of bark (Ora.)
	<i>Alstonia scholaris</i>	Chatiani	Tree	Jaundice	Leaf	Juice and Powder (Ora.)
Arecaceae	<i>Borassus flabellifer</i>	Tala	Tree	Contraceptive	Male inflorescence	Fruit, leaf juice (Ora.)
Asclepiadaceae	<i>Calotropis gigantea</i>	Arakha	Shrub	Stomach problem	Root, bark	Juice (Ora.)
Asparagaceae	<i>Asparagus racemosus</i>	Satabari	Climber	Stomach problems	Root	Powder, juice (Ora.)
Asphodelaceae	<i>Aloe vera</i>	Ghikuanri	Herb	Digestion, treat burns, clean acne	Stem	Stem juice (Ext., Ora.)
Asteraceae	<i>Ageratum conyzoides</i>	Pokasunga	Herb	Skin infection	Leaf	Juice (Ora.)
	<i>Helianthus annuus</i>	Surya mukhi	Herb	Common cold	Seed	Seed paste, juice (Ext., Ora.)
Cactaceae	<i>Opuntia dillenii</i>	Nagafeni	Herb	Swelling of joints	Phylloclade	Juice (Ora.)
Caesalpiniaceae	<i>Bauhinia variegata</i>	Kanchana	Tree	Mouth problem, stomach	Root, bark	Leaf, stem juice (Ora.)
	<i>Cassia fistula</i>	Sunari	Tree	Diabetes, dysentery, blood poisoning, antiseptic	Whole plant	Seed powder, leaves extract, (Ora., Ext.)
	<i>Saraca asoca</i>	Ashoka	Tree	Bleeding piles,,Dysmenorrhea	Bark	Powder (Ora., Ext.)
	<i>Bauhinia racemosa</i>	Anmata	Tree	Diarrhoea	Leaf	Leaf juice (Ora.)
Combretaceae	<i>Angeissus latifolia</i>	Dharua	Tree	Diarrhoea	Bark, gum, leaf	Gum with a cup of water for lactation
Corneaeceae	<i>Alangium salvifolium</i>	Ankula	Tree	Wound, infection due to snake bite	Leaf, Bark	Powder (Oral)
Cucurbitaceae	<i>Coccinia grandis</i>	Jungle kunduri	Climber	Pain, wound	Leaf, fruit, root	Juice (Ora.)
Convolvulaceae	<i>Cuscuta reflexa</i>	Nirmuli	Climber	Scrotum treatment	Whole plant	Stem extract (Ora.)

Family	Scientific name	Local name	Habit	Medicinal use	Part used	Methods of use
Dilleniaceae	<i>Dillenia pentagyna</i>	Rai	Herb	Child birth problem	Seed	Seed (Ora.)
Ebenaceae	<i>Diospyros melanoxylon</i>	Kendu	Tree	Night blindness	Stem, fruit, bark	Fruit (Ora.), Stem and Bark (Ext.)
	<i>Diospyros malabarica</i>	Kalikendu	Tree	Dysentery	Leaf, bark	Bark extract (Ora.)
Euphorbiaceae	<i>Antidesma bunius</i>	Mutta	Tree	Skin infection, diarrhoea	Bark, fruit	Juice, Bark paste (Ext., Ora.)
	<i>Aporosa octandra</i>	Makania	Tree	Bone fracture	Leaf	Paste (Ext.)
	<i>Croton roxburghii</i>	Putuli	Shrub	Diarrhoea	Leaf, seed	Seed oil (Ora.)
	<i>Macaranga peltata</i>	Manda	Tree	Skin infection	Leaf	Juice (Ext., Ora.)
	<i>Phyllanthus emblica</i>	Amla	Tree	Improving eye	Leaf, fruit, seed	Juice, fruit (Ora.)
	<i>Euphorbia neriiifolia</i>	Siju	Shrub	Rheumatism	Latex	Latex (Ext.)
	Fabaceae	<i>Trigonella foenum-graecum</i>	Methi	Herb	Constipation, hair fall	Leaf
Lamiaceae	<i>Colebrookea oppositifolia</i>	Maranga	Shrub	wounds, cuts, bruises, treatment of fracture, and traumatic injuries	Root, Leaf	Root paste (Ora.)
	<i>Gmelina arborea</i>	Gambhari	Tree	Wound treatment	Root, bark	Root paste (Ext.)
Lauraceae	<i>Cinnamomum tamala</i>	Tejpatra	Tree	Digestion, Cough, Dental	Leaf	Inhale, Ext. and Ora.
Lecythidaceae	<i>Barringtonia acutangula</i>	Hinjal	Tree	Skin infection	Leaf, Bark, seed	Aqueous extract (Ora.)
	<i>Careya arborea</i>	Kumbhi	Tree	Skin infection	Leaf	Ora. and Ext. as an embrocation
Malvaceae	<i>Bombax ceiba</i>	Simili	Tree	Menstruation	Fleshy root	Juice (Ora.)
	<i>Hibiscus rosa-sinensis</i>	Mandara	Shrub	Blood pressure, weight loss	Leaf, flower	Leaf and flower paste (Ext., Ora.)
Melastomataceae	<i>Melastoma malabathrium</i>	Korali	Shrub	Skin infection	Leaf	Decoction of leaf (Ora.)
Meliaceae	<i>Azadirachita indica</i>	Neem	Tree	Cold, chickenpox	Leaf, fruit	Juice, paste (Ora. and Ext.)
Mimosaceae	<i>Acacia catechu</i>	Khairo	Tree	Night blindness	Stem, bark	Juice (Ora.)
	<i>Mimosa pudica</i>	Lajakuli	Herb	Stomach problem	Root	Root paste (Ora.)
Moraceae	<i>Artocarpus heterophyllus</i>	Panasa	Tree	Heart problem	Leaf, Fruit	Ashes of leaf, fruit (Ora.)

Family	Scientific name	Local name	Habit	Medicinal use	Part used	Methods of use
Moraceae	<i>Ficus religiosa</i>	Aswasta	Tree	Skin infection	Stem, bark	Stem, Bark Paste (Ext.)
	<i>Ficus racemosa</i>	Dembru	Tree	Tonic disease	Areal part	Juice, Paste (Ora., Ext.)
Moringaceae	<i>Moringa oleifera</i>	Sujana saga	Tree	Diabetes	Leaf, fruit	Leaf paste, Fruit (External, Ora.)
Myrtaceae	<i>Syzygium cumini</i>	Jammun	Tree	Common cold, diabetes	Fruit, seed	Fruit and seed powder (Ora.)
	<i>Psidium guajava</i>	Pijuli	Tree	Headache	Flower	Flower smoke (Inhale), fruit (Ora.)
Nelumbonaceae	<i>Nelumbo nucifera</i>	Padma	Herb	Blood dysentery	Flower	Flower, Leaf (Ext., Ora.)
Oleaceae	<i>Nyctanthes arborescens</i>	Gangasiuli	Shrub	Dysentery	Flower, Leaf	Leaf juice and Dried fruit, flower (Ora.)
Poaceae	<i>Oryza sativa</i>	Dhana	Grass	Blood pressure, dysentery	Seed	Seed paste (Ext., Ora.)
	<i>Cynodon dactylon</i>	Duba	Grass	Nasal problem	Leaf	Leaf paste, juice (Ext., Ora.)
	<i>Vetiveria zizanioides</i>	Bena ghasa	Grass	Scorpion bite	Leaf, Root	Leaf smoke (Inhale), paste (Ext.)
	<i>Bambusa tulda</i>	Bans	Tree	Blood purification	Internodes white crystal	Decoction of leaves and nodes (Ora.)
Punicaceae	<i>Punica granatum</i>	Bedna	Tree	Cough, expel tapeworm	Seed, Fruit	Seed paste (Ext.), Fruit (Ora.)
Rubiaceae	<i>Anthocephalus chinensis</i>	Kadamba	Tree	Stomach pain, Cancer	Stem, bark	Bark juice (Ora.)
Rutaceae	<i>Citrus aurantifolia</i>	Lembu	Shrub	Common cold, tinnitus	Seed, Fruit	Fruit juice (External, Ora.)
	<i>Citrus grandis</i>	Tava	Shrub	Digestion	Fruit	Peel Paste (Ext., Ora.)
	<i>Aegle marmelos</i>	Bela	Tree	Digestion, chronic, diarrhoea	Fruit, leaf	Ora.
Sapotaceae	<i>Limonia acidissima</i>	Kaintha	Tree	Common cold, dysentery, diabetes	Leaf, Fruit	Fruit (Ora.), leaf juice and paste (Ext.)
	<i>Madhuca longifolia</i>	Mohula	Tree	Common cold	Leaf, bark	Infusion of bark (Ora.)
Smilacaceae	<i>Smilax perfoliata</i>	Ramdatun	Climber	Teeth cleaning	Root, leaf	Leaf juice and root (Ora.)

Family	Scientific name	Local name	Habit	Medicinal use	Part used	Methods of use
Solanaceae	<i>Datura stramonium</i>	Dudhura	Shrub	Ear problem	Seed	Seed juice (Ext.)
	<i>Solanum lycopersicum</i>	Tomato	Herb	Heart disease, breast cancer	Fruit	Juice (Ora.)
Zingiberaceae	<i>Curcuma longa</i>	Haldi	Herb	Wound, pain	Root	Juice, powder, leaf (Inhale, Ext., Ora.)
	<i>Zingiber officinale</i>	Ada	Herb	Cough,	Rhizome	Juice (Ora.)

Ext.- Externally, Ora.- Orally

Table 3. Percentage occurrence

Family	Percentage occurrence
Acanthaceae	1.44
Anacardiaceae	4.34
Amaryllidaceae	1.44
Apiaceae	1.44
Apocynaceae	4.34
Arecaceae	1.44
Asclepiadaceae	1.44
Asparagaceae	1.44
Asphodelaceae	1.44
Asteraceae	2.89
Cactaceae	1.44
Caesalpiniaceae	1.44
Combretaceae	1.44
Cornaceae	1.44
Cucurbitaceae	1.44
Convolvulaceae	1.44
Dilleniaceae	1.44
Ebenaceae	2.89
Euphorbiaceae	5.79
Fabaceae	7.24
Lamiaceae	2.89

Family	Percentage occurrence
Lauraceae	1.44
Lecythidaceae	2.89
Lythraceae	1.44
Malvaceae	2.89
Melastomataceae	1.44
Meliaceae	1.44
Mimosaceae	1.44
Moraceae	4.34
Moringaceae	1.44
Myrtaceae	2.89
Nelumbonaceae	1.44
Oleaceae	1.44
Poaceae	5.79
Rubiaceae	1.44
Rutaceae	5.79
Sapotaceae	1.44
Smilacaceae	1.44
Solanaceae	2.89
Zingiberaceae	2.89

Fig. 2. Percentage of species in each family

Fig. 3. Methods of in taking the plants as medicine

Fig. 4. Different plant parts used

Fig. 5. Different forms of in taking plant parts

% occurrence of Medicinal plants

Fig. 6. Habits of Medicinal plants

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

We are thankful to Mr. Santosh Joshi (IFS), Divisional Forest Officer, Divisional Forest Office, Baripada, Mayurbhanj, Odisha for his moral supports and permission to conduct the whole study. We are also thankful to Mr. Rabi Narayan Mohanty, Range officer and all the staff of Deuli Forest Range Office for their kind support and help. The authors are fortunate enough to get constant encouragement and moral supports from batchmates like Banajyotshna Pradhan and Partha Sarathi Mohanta.

REFERENCES

- Chopra, R.N. and Chopra, I.C. 1982. Indigenous Drugs of India. 2nd Ed, New Delhi. *Br. Med. J.* **12**; 2(4162): 491-492.
- Chopra, R.N., Nayar, S.L. and Chopra, I.C. 1956. *Glossary of Indian Medicinal Plants*. CSIR, New Delhi.
- Gamble, J.S. and Fischer, C.E.C. 1915-36. *Flora of Madras Presidency* **1**(1): 682
- Girach, R.D., Aminuddin Ahmed, M., Brahmam, M. and Misra, M.K. 1996. Native phytotherapy among rural population of district Bhadrak, Odisha. In: Jain, S.K. (Ed.), *Ethnobiology in Human Welfare*, Deep Publications, New Delhi **1**(1): 162-164.
- Haines, H.H. 1921-25. *The Botany of Bihar and Odisha*, Arnold and Sons and West Nirman, London.
- Manjunath, T.N. 1990. Importance of Traditional Medicines. *J. Econ. Bot. Phytochem.* **1**(1): 51-52.
- Mohapatra, M. 2019. Ethno-botanical study in some villages of Ganjam district, Odisha State. *J. Emerg. Technol. Innov. Res.* **6**(2): 189-204.
- Panigrahy, J. and Behera, S.K. 2016. Ethnomedicinal study of some medicinal plants from Kandhamal district, Odisha. *Int. J. Herbal Med.* **4**(5): 36-40.
- Pattanaik, C., Reddy, C.S. and Dhal, N.K. 2008. Phytomedicinal study of coastal sand dune species of Odisha. *Indian J. Tradit. Knowl.* **7**(1): 263-268.
- Sahoo, A.K. 1986. Plant resources of Kandhamal district (Odisha) some suggestion to develop cottage industries in tribal localities. *Odisha Rev.* **43**(4): 39-44.
- Sahu. S.C. and Pattanaik. S.K. 2011. Ethnobotanical study of medicinal plants in the coastal districts of Odisha. *Curr. Bot.* **2**(9): 1-4.
- Saxena, H.O. and Dutta, P.K. 1975. Studies on the ethnobotany of Odisha. *Bull. Bot. Surv. India* **17** (1-4): 124-131.
- Saxena, H.O. and Brahmam, M. 1994-96. *The Flora of Orissa*. Regional Research Laboratory, Bhubaneswar, Odisha and Forest Department Corporation, Odisha.
- Warrier, P.K., Nambiar, V.P.K. and Ramankutty, C. 1994-96. *Indian Medicinal Plants*, Madras, Orient Longman Ltd.